

DEFINITION OF MYTH, ITS ORIGIN, FUNCTIONS, AND TYPES

G.Djoldasova
PhD, docent

N.Amangeldieva
Student of KSU

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Abstract: *Following contemporary trends, we do not underestimate the significance of the objects with which we seek to surround ourselves. For modern humans, it remains crucial not only to form an aesthetic perception through the objects with which we interact, but also to preserve the need to feel the significance of those things that surround us. This natural desire to express our formed aesthetic ideals and beliefs through the forms we interact with constantly persists.*

Keywords: *mythology in culture, myths and legends, mechanisms of the universe, socio-compensatory function.*

At the early stages of human social development, mythology became the only way to understand the world. The term "myth" comes from the Greek word meaning "tradition, legend" [1, p.97]. Myths are narrative tales in which the interaction of humans with nature and its creation is revealed, along with stories about gods, heroes, and mythical creatures. Through myths, humans understand the higher origins of weather conditions and form moral values. The presence of mythology in a people's culture is typical of the archaic primitive era, which defines life values and the peculiarities of perception during that time.

Myths existed for everyone in the world. Ancient legends about the gods and mythical beings provided explanations for many events and natural catastrophes of the time. They shaped society, created the concept of values, and fostered social and spiritual unity, as myths are based not only on human fears and phobias but also on the desire to possess and control the forces of nature. Thus, myths and legends became an effective means of preserving the balance between nature and humanity. But why were myths created, and why did people believe in their truth? Most often, they believed that these stories demonstrated everything that really existed. Myths are not randomly invented tales; they never arise without reason. More often than not, they reflect the knowledge acquired by people, their observations, and the experience accumulated over the years. Humans have always sought the meaning of life, asking questions about their purpose since birth, why they live, and what role destiny has prepared for them. Troubled by these questions, humans experience profound despair, realizing they have no answers. For this reason, societies from the beginning of

creation wrote stories that revealed human life within the broader, higher unity of the world, determining the basis of existence and giving meaning to human life.

According to religious scholar Frederick Kuenz [4, p.156], four main directions can be identified that define mythology:

1. The creation of myths is often rooted in the fear of death or loss;
2. The most important and profound myths tell about the highest emotions and states of the spirit, which inadvertently urge us to go beyond our existing life experience;
3. Myths educate and teach how to act and what choices to make;
4. Mythology is closely intertwined with sacred rituals and mysteries: sacred actions. A well-constructed and retold mythology creates conditions for the sustainable balance of our mental and moral worldview, further creating the conditions for choices and actions in both the physical and spiritual worlds.

Any mythology tells of another world beyond our own, which is interconnected with ours, influencing and complementing each other. The belief in the existence of this all-encompassing reality, which transcends life and death and involves gods and mythical beings, is the foundation of any mythology. Thus, mythology serves as a source of support during difficult life events. In ancient times, it impacted people by allowing them to determine the value of their lives and find their purpose. Each of us wants to know how we came into existence – our ancestors wrote stories about their forebears. When the question arises about what lies ahead for us, myths about the other world and the afterlife are born. And when we seek answers to extraordinary events in our world, we transcend the ordinary. Thus, humans live their everyday lives within a broader moral unity of emotions, feelings, and thoughts. The myth becomes an excellent tool for perceiving the world from the ancient times of society's culture – the concept of *alētheia* – truth and existence, i.e., myth acquires the meaning of a certain doctrine and the primary structure of human thought at that time.

Relevance and Value of Myths Today:

Myths have not lost their relevance in the modern world. In contemporary society, myths remain as significant as ever. There is no single unified theory of myth creation, but several hypotheses are proposed for studying its structure:

The philosophy of the world theory, created by the Italian scholar Giambattista Vico, reveals the specificity and essence of the myth – as a fantasy or game that arose from intuitive perceptions of the presence of higher forces and the fear of their interaction with humans.

Barenbaum [1, p.169] identified animism as the basis of myths – the belief in a soul in every inanimate object. He characterized myths as primitive perceptions of the existing world. Baturin believed that myths arise from insufficient knowledge of the origins of phenomena and the lack of opportunities to study them. All these conclusions are the result of the work of 19th-century philosophers and sociologists [2, p.175].

One of the most significant events in 20th-century anthropology and sociology was the recognition of myths' vital role in ancient cultures: they connect religious beliefs, explain established moral and ethical norms of behavior, affirm the importance of rituals, traditions, and religious actions, and encapsulate rules for human and societal conduct. Thus, a myth is an aware social structure based on socio-ethical norms of behavior, not a product of childish imagination. Structuralism focuses on the local ethnic study of mythological foundations, rather than determining the meaning of each myth separately. The most attention has been given to binomial, dyadic comparisons: lower and upper, male and female, cold and hot, living and dead. These oppositions explain the vivid conflicts in the consciousness that our minds attempt to reconcile.

The functions of myths define their properties according to specific categories of qualifications [3, p.15].

- **Socio-practical function:** This is the primary function to which all others are attached. It defines the integrity and unity of the collective through the self-definition of the individual in the social subsystem, consisting of people with shared social traits, as well as with the community, state, surrounding world, religious symbols, and events from the lives of our ancestors. It provides self-awareness and perception of the individual as an integral part of the grand mechanism of the universe. This function promotes humanity's ability to exist in society and nature.

- **Ideological-pragmatic function:** In this function, mythology serves as a means of influencing society. It is crucial for balancing the cultural-mythological image of things as all-encompassing and unchanging, for explaining the system of authority and governance, structuring politics, and defining the socio-political framework of society.

- **Cognitive function:** In this case, the myth is a tool for studying and mastering the world. Understanding is more important here than studying, as it encompasses the study of the world through knowledge and the emotional component, as well as the mental and practical degree of perception and interaction with nature.

- **Worldview function:** World perception is divided into three directions: religion, philosophy, and myth. Myth arises from non-verbal social perception of the world and illustrates everything around us, based on cognitive study and interaction with reality.

- **Axiological function:** In other words, the evaluative function, which sorts phenomena and interactions between humans and reality, defining the level of influence and relationship of a particular event. The criteria for evaluation include the interests of the collective, family, generation, and attitudes toward life and death. The impact of a particular myth on a person is conditioned by its importance concerning life and the individual's needs.

- **Aesthetic function:** This function idealizes the cultural essence of humanity. The most significant here is the identification of vivid images in the myth, as the presence of rich descriptions reveals a deeper and more beautiful aspect of human values.

- **Communicative function:** This function is essential for the demonstration and perception of myths. It is one of the most important properties of a myth and its understanding. A myth, perceived as a unique form of interaction with humans, establishes a particular direction and mood for interacting with people and the world. A vivid example is the mysteries and rituals conducted within a small community.

- **Mobilizing function:** This function generates colorful images through the feelings and perceptions of society, motivating people to engage in an activity, instilling in them determination and faith. It manifests only when unconditional trust and unquestioning dedication to a cause arise in people.

- **Socio-compensatory function:** One of the most essential functions for revealing the psychological sensation of oneself. This function involves significant self-work, allowing the release of internal anxieties and contradictions stemming from life's difficulties. Many rituals were performed primarily to form this "purified" state of the soul and were used to achieve harmony with reality. The socio-compensatory function leads people from the world of reality into a world of fantasy, where the burdens of real life have no place.

In addition to dividing myths by their functions, myths can be classified by type and significance. For example, there are solar, lunar, and astral myths, all concerning the origin of the sun, the moon, and constellations. The majority of myths are considered cosmological, telling the story of the birth of the universe and the world. This includes theogonic myths – about gods and their influence on people. Other

categories include anthropological myths, which describe the appearance of humans in this world, and eschatological myths, which reveal the apocalypse, Ragnarok, and the end of the universe. Binary myths also fall under this category, where the creation and relationship between two polar opposites of life are discussed. Finally, there are calendar myths.

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